

Alignment Between Written and Learned Curriculum of the Caregiver Training Course in Health Alliance Training Center

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Abstract

While administrators and faculty hold high regard for actual instructional delivery, educational experts place a premium on the development of an effective curriculum, as it serves as the springboard of the teaching and learning process. To determine the degree of alignment between the written and learned curriculum of the Caregiver Training Course in Health Alliance Training Center (HATC), the researchers examined the academic performance of the graduates. This was done to assess the extent to which the objectives stipulated in the written curriculum were achieved and the quality standards were met. HATC, as an educational institution, designed the caregiving curriculum with the ultimate goal of producing certified caregivers and nursing assistants who are equipped with the theoretical knowledge and practical training necessary for success in the industry. To describe the learned curriculum developed among the graduates, qualitative data were gathered through open-ended, semi-structured interviews with 10 HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course graduates. The three themes generated from the participants' narratives describe the knowledge and skill acquisition, as well as the behavioral changes, that participants experienced after completing the caregiving course. These correspond with the three major learning components of the curriculum, as measured in the grading system: Theme 1 for knowledge or cognitive, Theme 2 for skills or psychomotor, and Theme 3 for attitude or affective. This alignment closes the gap between what teachers believe students should learn and what students actually accomplish, as recommended by the William & Mary School of Education (2024). Accordingly, the written and learned curricula of HATC's Caregiver Training Course were found to be highly aligned in terms of developing the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of the graduates because they were able to achieve their main goal of changing career path, that is to be efficient caregivers that served as their ticket to migrating to first world countries.

Keywords: written curriculum, learned curriculum, academic performance, caregiver training course, Health Alliance Training Center

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INTRODUCTION

In both work and school settings, several types of curricula co-exist. Among those technically defined by educational experts are the recommended curriculum, which pertains to what is prescribed by scholars and professional organizations; the written curriculum, referring to state and locally produced documents; the taught curriculum, which is the actual instruction delivered by teachers; the supported curriculum, which refers to resources that support the curriculum; the assessed curriculum, which reflects tests and

performance measures; the learned curriculum, which encompasses what students actually learn; and the hidden curriculum, or the unintended curriculum. Of all those mentioned, educators are arguably most attuned to the learned curriculum, which serves as the basis for their choices in how they identify and respond to students' needs. However, there should be congruence among all forms of the curriculum to ensure quality education (Glatthorn, 2000).

The phrase "learned curriculum" refers to all behavioral, mental, and ethical shifts brought

about by educational experiences. It therefore encompasses the knowledge, skills, and understanding that learners gain from both the intentional and hidden curricula. Everything students learn at the end of a course is part of the learned curriculum. This includes not only the material and skills acquired during the course but also any additional modifications to their mindset and psychological state. The gap between what teachers expect students to learn and what they actually accomplish is one that needs to be bridged (William & Mary School of Education, 2024). The changing needs of each individual student, as well as the demands of society, call for periodic curriculum updates and alignment by educators and schools. The significance of curriculum development in improving teaching and learning is increasing as global change accelerates. The way students are trained to assume their roles and responsibilities must adapt quickly to align with the evolving world. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) asserts in its "Education 2030" position statement that "the notion of curriculum should be developed from 'predetermined and static' to 'adaptable and dynamic' (Howells, 2018).

The Health Alliance Training Center (HATC) in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) offers training and technical assistance to Filipinos who intend to pursue a career in caregiving and as nursing aides. KSA ranks as the top destination for Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs). Since 2017, HATC has catered to hundreds of OFWs who changed career paths—often professionals in the Philippines who chose to work as caregivers abroad due to higher compensation. It is recognized by TESDA overseas to conduct training in support of the government's reintegration program. At present, HATC continues to strengthen its affiliation with TESDA as it offers caregiving courses in two of its KSA branches—Al Khobar and Jeddah. It has produced hundreds of graduates who had no prior background in the healthcare industry but managed to secure employment not only in Saudi Arabia but also in Western countries and the United States. This success continues to attract more Filipino OFWs to consider a career shift to caregiving.

In 2021, the Bureau of Labor Statistics projected that care and home health assistant employment is expected to increase by 34% between 2019 and 2029. In addition, Dewdrop (2023) asserted that the need for caregiving services is growing, and it is becoming increasingly evident that an effective caregiver training course is necessary to fulfill the specific needs of care recipients and to ensure their safety, health, and overall well-being. Caregiving is a demanding and multifaceted role that requires various competencies, knowledge, and practical skills and caregivers must navigate challenges such as stress management, emotional regulation, balancing job and family responsibilities, effective communication, and the provision of high-quality care. Therefore, caregivers must receive proper training and support to manage these challenges and enhance the caregiving experience (Faster Capital, 2024).

As the demand for caregivers continue to rise, the rigor of training courses has become a prime concern for educational institutions and concerned agencies. This situation calls for an elevated and updated curriculum design that entails purposefully planning, organizing, and crafting learning strategies, processes, and materials aimed at realizing the desired learning and performance outcomes (American Educational Research Association, n.d.). A significant stage in this process is periodic review and evaluation to assess the curriculum's impact on teaching and learning, allowing for revisions to ensure optimum quality and outcomes (Moore, 2022).

This study was conceptualized on the premise that the learned curriculum is an essential touchstone for improving the current design of caregiving training courses. The knowledge, skills, and understanding that graduates have gained—as well as the shifts in values and perspectives resulting from their learning experiences—serve as an indispensable basis and powerful feedback for curriculum designers and administrators in enhancing the written curriculum of a caregiver training course. This study aimed to determine the alignment between the written curriculum and

the learned or experiential curriculum of Overseas Filipino Workers who shifted from their previous professions to caregiving after completing a Reintegration Caregiver Training Course. The researcher described the delivery of the written curriculum and how it aligned with the development of the participants learned curriculum, particularly regarding changes in values, perceptions, and behavior that occurred as a result of their educational experiences. This included what they understood, learned, and retained from both the intentional and hidden curriculum.

LITERATURES

Curriculum. Since the inception of curriculum studies, the term "curriculum" has been used to refer to a wide range of meanings, making it perhaps the most complex to define. According to UNESCO (2013), curriculum is defined as the "inventory of activities implemented to design, organize and plan an education or training action, including definition of learning objectives, content, methods (including assessment) and material, as well as arrangements for training teachers and trainers." Ornstein and Hopkins (2016) defined curriculum as a structure that organizes learning experiences, objectives, subject matter, and assessment methods—viewing curriculum as a system while Erturk (2015) referred curriculum as a methodical approach for teaching-learning activities aimed at educating learners within a specific time frame.

Upon examining the diverse interpretations of the term in academic literature, and upon review of various literatures, one can discern that the concept of curriculum has been approached as comprised of the following: subjects taught in schools, content, subject area, materials, all school-planned activities, and experiences that students acquire while attending classes (Marzooghi, 2016). Curriculum definitions from various perspectives indicate ongoing efforts to arrive at a more unified definition. Analysis of these definitions reveals that some emphasize learners' experiences, while others highlight the skills necessary for adult life preparation (Yasar & Aslan, 2021).

Types of Curriculum. Some important distinctions regarding the types of curriculum may have first been suggested by Goodlad (1979). In his analysis, Goodlad identified five distinct types of curriculum planning. The *ideological curriculum* represents the ideal curriculum, as defined by scholars and educators, and reflects funded knowledge. The *formal curriculum* is officially accepted by state and local education boards and reflects societal interests. The *perceived curriculum* is what instructors, parents, and others believe the curriculum to be. The *operational curriculum* is what is actually delivered, hour by hour, in the classroom. Finally, the *experiential curriculum* refers to the curriculum as learners engage with it.

Although these distinctions are significant, curriculum developers may find the concepts somewhat confusing, and the categories may not be entirely helpful. The terms "recommended curriculum," "written curriculum," "supported curriculum," "taught curriculum," "tested curriculum," and "learned curriculum" are more applicable in the current educational setting, albeit with slightly different meanings. The written, supported, taught, and tested curricula constitute the *intentional curriculum*—that is, the curriculum consciously planned by the educational institution. In contrast, the *hidden curriculum* typically results from unintended lessons and is not a product of deliberate effort.

Wilson (2013) referred to the *recommended curriculum* as *rhetorical curriculum* and noted that its components may include ideas from politicians, school administrators, and other influential figures. This curriculum can also emerge from professional organizations that contribute to content development or from decisions made in response to public speeches and policy reports. Public efforts to modernize teaching may also influence rhetorical curricula. In the Philippines, examples include curricula recommended by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) or the Department of Education (DepEd). Under specific circumstances, a university or school, along with legislative bodies such as assemblies or

councils, may endorse a course or academic program deemed essential for national integrity, environmental protection, or sustainable development (Alvior, 2020).

A written curriculum is a critical component of any educational course. It serves as a guide for educators, providing structure to facilitate instruction and ensure consistency in the classroom. The written curriculum has two primary goals: to define the knowledge and skills students should acquire and to provide teachers with instructional guidance. By clearly outlining learning objectives, the written curriculum supports student development and achievement and provides a framework for assessment, helping educators identify areas where students may need additional support (Alvior, 2023).

The tested curriculum refers to knowledge evaluated through standardized tests, district assessments, and teacher-made exams. The *supported curriculum* encompasses the resources allocated to support curriculum delivery. These include time allocation per subject, personnel distribution, and learning materials such as textbooks and supplies. It also involves the use of resources—people, time, and materials—to implement both the written and delivered curricula (Glatthorn et al., 2012).

The taught curriculum refers to what students encounter in the classroom. In a qualitative study conducted by Bamkin (2020) to explore moral education practices in Japan, he concluded that the taught curriculum—or operational curriculum—is what teachers deliver daily. Teachers are thus seen as the key implementers of the curriculum. In his article “Seven School Curriculum Types and Their Classroom Implications,” Alvior (2020) describes the taught curriculum as the way teachers bring the written curriculum to life, including all that is taught and enacted in the classroom.

Among all these types, educators are arguably most attuned to the *written curriculum*, which serves as a vital guide for consistent

instructional delivery, and the learned curriculum, which informs educators' understanding of students' needs and their subsequent responses. Still, there must be alignment among all curriculum types to ensure quality education (Glatthorn, 2000).

The learned curriculum encompasses all behavioral, mental, and ethical changes resulting from educational experiences. It includes the knowledge, skills, and understanding students acquire from both the intentional and hidden curricula. Everything that students internalize by the end of a course—including knowledge, skills, and shifts in mindset and attitudes—is part of the learned curriculum. A key educational challenge is bridging the gap between what teachers intend students to learn and what students actually learn (William & Mary School of Education, 2024).

In school turnaround contexts, many educators find it difficult to discern which strategies are effective or ineffective (Salmonowicz, 2009). Although classroom circumstances may vary, minor discrepancies between the taught and learned curricula often occur.

Importance of Evaluation in Developing a Quality Curriculum. In a publication series by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), Stabback (2016) explained that a high-quality curriculum focuses on three major components: knowledge, skills, and values. It should enable students to learn and develop the information, skills, and values, as well as the related capabilities and competencies, to lead meaningful and productive lives. The caliber of learning attained by students and the degree to which they apply that learning to their personal, social, physical, cognitive, moral, psychological, and emotional development are important markers of curriculum success. A high-quality curriculum optimizes the potential for successfully improving learning.

Tunnell (2022) further argues that an effective, student-driven curriculum adapts to an evolving world, contains research-based

teaching techniques, encourages collaboration, meets students' needs, and establishes quantifiable objectives. The curriculum should serve as a guide for teachers in aligning instruction with fast-paced trends, innovations, and essential skills required by students both now and in the future. It should also specify teaching approaches and strategies that are proven effective through research. An effective curriculum should be the product of collaborative expertise and efforts among stakeholders—teachers, administrators, parents, and communities. Moreover, it should recognize the diversity of learners and be designed with consideration of students' strengths and weaknesses. Lastly, it should have realistic and measurable objectives and meet state and national standards.

It is pivotal that educational institutions periodically gauge the effectiveness of the curriculum, as this reflects the extent to which learning objectives are met. Through periodic evaluation, educational institutions can align the content with the changing demands of industries, ensuring that students are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to face real-world challenges. With this, data on students' progress become available to guide teachers in adjusting teaching strategies based on identified strengths and weaknesses. Improving the curriculum enhances the overall quality of education, and without evaluation, areas for improvement would not be identified (American Profession Guide, 2024).

One crucial way of assessing the curriculum is by analyzing students' performance data in the form of grades, attendance records, and feedback. Such data enable teachers to track student progress and provide valuable insights for making informed decisions to improve instructional strategies. Furthermore, these data also serve as useful references for curriculum adjustments, allowing teachers to understand the extent to which students have mastered the content and skills outlined in the curriculum. This contributes to a comprehensive analysis of the curriculum's effectiveness (American Profession Guide, 2024). Another form of data worth considering

in curriculum evaluation and development is graduates' performance in state-conducted board examinations, as this reflects two dimensions of quality teaching (Gibson et al., 2015).

Reintegration Caregiving Course. In the case of the HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course, a compact Caregiving/Nursing Assistant syllabus patterned after the TESDA Caregiving NC II Training Regulations served as the written curriculum. It was designed to equip students with knowledge on the fundamentals of caregiving, skills in providing care to the elderly and clients with special needs, and a positive attitude necessary to become effective and globally competitive caregivers in accordance with industry standards. The program consists of 786 hours of instruction, divided into eight months or 32 weeks, and covers seven modules: Introduction to Health Care, Understanding People in Our Care, Understanding the Human Body, Promoting Safety, Nutrition and Assisting with Meals and Fluids, Principles of Medication Administration, and Special Care Situations.

Instructional delivery was commonly conducted through lecture-discussion, film viewing, and demonstrations. Students were assessed using the Knowledge (40%), Skills (50%), and Attitude (10%) matrix. Knowledge acquisition was graded based on monthly examinations and case presentations. Skills development was evaluated through practical and moving examinations, as well as nutrition presentations. Attitude was rated based on students' behavior and positive disposition during learning activities (see Appendix G for the complete list of topics).

METHODS

This study utilized a mixed-methods design, which entailed gathering, evaluating, and combining quantitative and qualitative data at various stages of the investigation. It is an approach that focuses on collecting, analyzing, and integrating both types of data in a single investigation. This design offers a greater understanding of the research problem, as the

quantitative method can strengthen the weaknesses of the qualitative method and vice versa. Once data is supported by numerical analysis and performed using statistical techniques, the issue of biases typically associated with qualitative interpretation can be mitigated. Conversely, the participants' actual experiences can provide support for and clarity on quantitative findings, which are typically lacking in depth (Creswell, 2003). Moreover, this study was explanatory in nature, as it aimed to investigate how and why a phenomenon occurs. By analyzing patterns, explanatory research enables researchers to develop hypotheses that can guide future inquiries.

Quantitative data were gathered from the results of written and practical examinations, final grades, number of graduates, NC II takers, and passers over the past five years. The researchers considered the records of all graduates of the HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course from 2019 to 2024. Document analysis was conducted on the results of written and practical examinations, as well as the number of graduates who have been employed as caregivers. To describe the overall performance of students enrolled in the program, the researcher employed basic statistical treatments such as frequency, percentage distribution, and weighted mean on the numerical data, which reflected written and practical examination scores, final grades, and NC II results. This step was necessary to determine the degree of alignment between the written and learned curriculum of the Caregiver Training Course in HATC.

Qualitative data were obtained from the verbatim transcriptions of participants' responses during one-on-one interviews, making caregiving course graduates the primary data source. the researcher employed purposive criterion sampling—a non-probability sampling technique in which participants are deliberately selected based on predefined criteria because they can provide meaningful insights into the research problem. The researcher intentionally chose only 10 graduates of the HATC Reintegration Caregiving

Course. An analysis of the verbatim transcriptions of the one-on-one interviews with the participants was carried out, following Schoch's (2020) recommended phases: describing, emergence of findings, coding, and comparing.

In integrating the quantitative and qualitative methods, the researcher applied the processes of merging, embedding, and connecting numerical and narrative data. After merging the results during interpretation and analysis, the researcher embedded qualitative data into the quantitative design, and vice versa. Finally, the researcher connected how the quantitative data led to qualitative insights and how the qualitative findings informed the quantitative outcomes (Creswell et al., 2003; Hanson et al., 2005; Plano Clark, 2005).

RESULTS

Academic Ratings and NC II Performance of HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course Graduates. The existing HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course curriculum focuses on the fundamentals of caregiving and nursing skills and assesses students based on three major components: knowledge, skills, and attitude. The table below presents the total number of graduates from both the Jeddah and Al Khobar HATC branches, along with their corresponding academic ratings and National Certification II performance.

Table 1
NC II Performance of HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course Graduates

HATC Branch	Number of Graduates	Academic Ratings				Certification		
		Knowledge 40%	Skills 50%	Attitude 10%	Final Grade 100%	Number of NC II Takers	Number of NC II Passers	Passing Rate (%)
Al-Khobar	519	32.12	43.38	9.18	84.69	63	63	100
Jeddah	142	31.61	41.56	8.86	82.03	82	82	100
Total	661	31.87	42.47	9.02	83.36	145	145	100

Table 1 shows the academic ratings of all HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course graduates and the results of the National Qualification for Caregiving NC II certification from 2019 to 2024. The final grade average of 519 graduates from the Al-Khobar branch was 84.69%, which is

verbally interpreted as satisfactory, while the 142 graduates from the Jeddah branch obtained a final grade average of 82.03%, resulting in a satisfactory overall average of 83.36%. In terms of National Certification II performance, all 145 takers—63 in Al-Khobar and 82 in Jeddah—passed.

Based on the above data, it can be concluded that HATC's caregiving written curriculum aligns with international standards for an effective curriculum. First, it satisfies the three major components (knowledge, skills, values) of a quality curriculum as identified by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in a publication by Stabback (2016). The grading system implemented since the first batch of graduates was divided into three components: knowledge, skills, and attitude. This supports the notion that a high-quality curriculum should enable students to develop knowledge, skills, and values, as well as related capabilities and competencies, to lead meaningful and productive lives. The caliber of learning attained by students and the degree to which they apply that learning to their personal, social, physical, cognitive, moral, psychological, and emotional development are important markers of curriculum success. A high-quality curriculum optimizes the likelihood of successfully improving learning outcomes.

Secondly, the overall final grades of the graduates reflect the effectiveness of the written curriculum. As the American Profession Guide (2024) asserts, one crucial way of assessing curriculum quality is by analyzing students' performance data—such as grades, attendance records, and feedback. Students' performance data enable teachers to track progress and provide valuable insights for making informed instructional decisions. Furthermore, such data are useful references for curriculum adjustment, as teachers gain a deeper understanding of the extent to which students have mastered the content and skills outlined in the curriculum, thereby contributing to the comprehensive analysis of curriculum effectiveness. The satisfactory ratings of students imply that the curriculum is effective

in meeting the qualifications set for caregivers; however, this also suggests that improvements are necessary to achieve optimum learning outcomes.

Lastly, the 100% passing rate of graduates strongly indicates that HATC's written curriculum adheres to the national standards for caregiving. This aligns with the findings of Gibson et al. (2015), which revealed that graduates' performance in state-conducted board examinations reflects the quality of the curriculum.

Alignment between the Written and Learned Curriculum. Table 2 below summarizes how the high degree of alignment between the written and learned curriculum was established using the qualitative and quantitative data gathered as evidence of learning.

Table 2
Alignment between the Written and Learned Curriculum

Learning Competency	Written Curriculum		Learned Curriculum	
	Subjects	Evidence of Learning	Theme	Evidence of Learning
Cognitive	- Module 1: Introduction to Health Care - Module 2: Understanding the Human Body-Chapter 1: Anatomy and Physiology - Module 3: Nutrition and Assisting with Meals and Fluids- Chapter 1: Food and Nutrition	31.87% out of 40% mastery level of students' knowledge acquisition based on examinations	Theme 1: Cognitive Domain Alignment	Narratives on how HATC equipped the non-health related participants with sufficient content knowledge about the different types of care setting that built their confidence in health care
	- Module 7: Special Care Situations - Module 3: Understanding the Human Body-Chapter 2: Measuring Vital Signs, Pain Assessment, Weight and Height Measurement - Module 4: Promoting Safety - Module 5: Nutrition and Assisting with Meals and Fluids- Chapter 2: Assisting with Meals and Fluids	42.47% out of 50% level of students' skill development based on examinations	Theme 2: Psychomotor Domain Alignment	Narratives on how HATC equipped the non-health related participants with skills as evidence
Psychomotor	- Module 6: Principles of Medication Administration - Module 2: Understanding People in Our Care	9.02% out of 10% development of positive attitude towards caregiving	Theme 3: Affective Domain Alignment	Narratives on how the participants who were initially driven by job opportunities and compensation found themselves fully immersed and dedicated their newly found career
	Course Description - The course is designed to equip students with knowledge on the fundamentals of caregiving, skills in providing care to elderly and clients with special needs, and positive attitude necessary to become effective and globally competitive caregivers in accordance with industry standards.	83.36% out of 100% satisfactory overall grade point average of graduates 100% passing rate in NC II Certification	Themes 1-3	-Immediate employment of graduates in Western countries and United States -Narratives expressing the participants' high level of satisfaction on HATC's Caregiving Training Course
Overall Realization of Curriculum Objectives				

As reflected in Table 2, the quantitative and qualitative data served as evidences of learning which established the high degree of alignment of the written and learned curriculum in terms of developing the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective competencies of students.

Cognitive Competencies. In developing cognitive competencies, three main modules and one chapter from Module 5 were taught to equip students with knowledge on the fundamentals of caregiving:

1. Module 1, *Introduction to Health Care*, which consists of seven chapters covering the following topics: Health Care Setting, Providing Care for People in Their Homes, Protecting the Recipients of Health Care,

being a Caregiver, communicating with People, Understanding Legal and Ethical Aspects of Health Care, and Caregiver Stress and Burnout;

2. Chapter 2 of Module 3, *Understanding the Human Body*, which covers Anatomy and Physiology;
3. Chapter 1 of Module 5, *Nutrition and Assisting with Meals and Fluids*, which covers Food and Nutrition; and,
4. Module 7, *Special Care Situations*, which consists of four chapters covering: Caring for Children with Special Needs, Providing Care for People with Specific Illnesses, Providing Care for People with Cognitive Changes or Dementia, and Providing Care for People at the End of Life.

To assess how much knowledge was acquired by the graduates, the researcher used the knowledge component (40%) of their grades, which averaged 31.87 for graduates from both the Jeddah and Al-Khobar branches. These grades were then compared with qualitative data in the form of participants' narratives, which were clustered to form Theme 1: Cognitive Domain Alignment. This theme explains how HATC equipped non-health-related participants with sufficient content knowledge that built their confidence in providing health care.

Psychomotor Competencies. In developing psychomotor competencies, four modules were taught to equip students with essential nursing skills:

1. Chapter 2 of Module 3, *Understanding the Human Body*, which covers Measuring Vital Signs, Pain Assessment, and Weight and Height Measurement;
2. Module 4, *Promoting Safety*, which consists of seven chapters covering: Controlling the Spread of Infection, Workplace Safety, maintaining a Comfortable Environment, Providing Restorative Care, assisting with Positioning and Transferring, assisting with

Personal Cleanliness and Grooming, and Assisting with Elimination;

3. Chapter 2 of Module 5, *Nutrition and Assisting with Meals and Fluids*, which covers Assisting with Meals and Fluids; and,
4. Module 6, *Principles of Medication Administration*, which consists of one chapter covering drug administration.

To assess skill development among graduates, the researcher used the skills component (50%) of their grades, which averaged 42.47 for graduates from both the Jeddah and Al-Khobar branches. These grades were then compared with qualitative data in the form of participants' narratives, which were clustered to form Theme 2: Psychomotor Domain Alignment. This theme delineates how HATC equipped the non-health-related participants with the skills essential to make them effective and efficient caregivers.

Affective Competencies. In developing affective competencies, one module was taught to inculcate a positive attitude toward caregiving:

1. Module 2, *Understanding People in Our Care*, consists of four chapters covering Human Growth and Development, Age-Specific Care, Human Basic Needs, and Culture and Diversity.

To assess the extent to which a positive attitude was inculcated among graduates, the researcher used the attitude component (10%) of their grades, which averaged 9.02 for graduates from both the Jeddah and Al-Khobar branches. These grades were compared with qualitative data in the form of participants' narratives, which were clustered to form Theme 3: Affective Domain Alignment. This theme communicates how participants, who were initially driven by job opportunities and compensation, found themselves fully immersed in and dedicated to their newly found careers.

Overall Realization of Curriculum Objectives. Through the process of merging, embedding, and connecting the quantitative and qualitative

data presented and analyzed, it can be concluded that the written curriculum is highly aligned with the learned curriculum of HATC Reintegration Caregiving Course graduates in terms of developing the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective competencies of students. As stated in the HATC syllabus, the course is designed to equip students with knowledge on the fundamentals of caregiving, skills in providing care to the elderly and clients with special needs, and a positive attitude necessary to become effective and globally competitive caregivers in accordance with industry standards.

The 83.36% satisfactory general weighted average of graduates, along with their 100% passing rate in the NC II certification, aligns strongly with the narratives of their positive experiences during and after the program. Not only did the non-health-related Filipino OFWs satisfactorily complete the course, but they also fulfilled their goal of shifting careers, as they were immediately hired as caregivers in Western countries and the United States. Thus, what the written curriculum intended to teach students is, in fact, what they actually learned. Moreover, the quantitative and qualitative data presented and analyzed reinforce that the written curriculum is highly aligned with the learned curriculum in developing the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of students. The numerical data reflect the extent to which the objectives and content of the written curriculum were achieved, and they closely correspond with the learned curriculum outcomes of the graduates. The overall satisfaction and overwhelming feedback from graduates affirm their satisfactory grades and excellent performance in the NC II Certification.

DISCUSSION

Cognitive Domain Alignment. The narratives of the participants explicitly conveyed that the objective of the written curriculum—providing graduates with theoretical knowledge on the fundamentals of caregiving—was fulfilled. Coming from entirely different industries, the participants initially expressed worries and inhibitions at the onset of their enrollment in the

caregiving course, which was driven by promising job opportunities and the influence of family and peers. The majority described themselves as having “zero knowledge” about caregiving and were uncertain about their ability to meet the demands of caregiving as a career. Despite these initial concerns, HATC equipped them with sufficient content knowledge that built their confidence in healthcare. The development of the cognitive domain in their learned curriculum is reflected in the following statements:

P1: I don't know that much about caregiving but when I was with HATC they were able to provide special lessons...I'm actually graduate of business administration major in accountancy, it's so totally different... I learned about the science of care giving and nursing assistance.

P2: Before I enrolled at Health Alliance Training Center, I was thinking about what will be my future, what will be my purpose...We can easily adapt it because of the right procedure and proper training that we gain from health alliance training center.

P3: My instructors made us feel like very welcome they are very willing to help us to learn how to be an efficient and effective caregiver...If there are topics we cannot understand, they are very willing to give the extra time to teach us...I can raise any questions ask some questions to clarify.

P6: At first, I was scared and anxious because I was not in the medical field and engineering is totally different.

P7: I started clueless. I only enrolled because of my friend's influence. At first I was even hesitant to enter the HATC building, because I had no idea what's in there. Good thing the HATC staff accommodated me well and explained what I should know as starter.

P8: I find it very interesting because I'm a BS Computer Science graduate. It's really a 360 degrees or 180 degrees rotation for me because I used to deal with only computers

before. Then when I joined or attended the caregiving program which is a medical field, it was a huge adjustment. However, I find it interesting and life-giving because whatever I learned from HATC I can real life. and another thing, I attended HATC program kase I intended to inspire my wife who is BS Nursing graduate.

P10: My experience in HATC it was fun, challenging, at the same time I learned. I learned a lot, especially the skills, theory, lahat po.

The career shift and narratives of the participants support the projections made by the Bureau of Labor Statistics in 2021 that care and home health assistant employment is expected to increase by 34% between 2019 and 2029. Moreover, this aligns with Dewdrop's (2023) assertion that the need for caregiving services is growing, and it is becoming increasingly evident that an effective caregiver training course is necessary to fulfill the specific needs of care recipients and to ensure their safety, health, and overall well-being.

Psychomotor Domain Alignment. More than knowledge acquisition, HATC's caregiving course places a premium on equipping graduates with the skills essential to making them effective and efficient caregivers. Thus, 50% of their grade component is based on their performance during practical examinations. During the interviews, the participants provided specific details on how they applied these skills in their actual caregiving jobs. The fact that the HATC graduates interviewed in Saudi Arabia are now employed in the United States and other Western countries indicates that the curriculum provides graduates with world-class training. This is supported by the following statements:

P1: I've learned specially how to assists patient if the patient is bedridden if the patient on a wheelchair how do you safely transfer them you should have like personalized care for special needs of a patient

P2: Every activity that I did to my client I always remember training from the HATC that's I used the training in HATC I used the experience how they train me.

P3: My experience in HATC, shaped me as caregiver and that prepared me to do my job well in Fakhri Hospital. My co-workers always compliment my performance. They are impressed with how I work and they have no complaints because they find me efficient.

P4: I learned a lot from the center especially the skills. I can apply them all now and those benefit me so much as a CNA here in America.

P8: Malaking tulong yung experience ko sa HATC, yung hands on namin, hands on training, yung cpr, yung mga ganon.

P9: I find it interesting and life-giving because whatever I learned from HATC I can apply in real life.

P10: The skills they taught us at HATC are beyond what they expect in other countries. It's really comprehensive, both in theories and skills.

The findings support the notion of Faster Capital (2024) that caregiving is a difficult and complex job that calls for a variety of abilities, knowledge, and skills. In order to overcome challenges and improve their caregiving experience, caregivers must have access to proper training and support.

Moreover, the narratives of the participants are strong indications of the effectiveness of HATC's caregiving curriculum, as it meets the qualifications specified by Tunnell (2022). Tunnell explained that an effective and student-driven curriculum adapts to an evolving world, incorporates research-based teaching techniques, encourages collaboration, meets students' needs, and establishes quantifiable objectives. The curriculum should serve as a guide for teachers in aligning their instruction with fast-paced trends, innovations, and the skills students need both now and in the future. It should also specify teaching approaches and strategies that are proven effective through research. An effective curriculum should be a product of collaborative expertise and effort among stakeholders—teachers, administration, parents, and communities. Moreover, it should

recognize the diversity of learners and be designed with consideration of students' strengths and weaknesses. Lastly, it should have realistic and measurable objectives and meet both state and national standards.

Affective Domain Alignment. The caregiving written curriculum not only focuses on content knowledge and skills development, but also emotionally prepares graduates by inculcating virtues necessary for caregivers to possess. These include trust, patience, compassion, responsibility, and professionalism. It is worth noting that, although caregiving was not the participants' first career choice, they eventually developed a passion for it. This could be attributed to the Principles of Care imparted during the course, as well as their genuine concern for their patients. The participants, who were initially driven by job opportunities and compensation, found themselves fully immersed in and dedicated to their newly found career. This change of heart is articulated in the following narratives:

P1: HATC teaches us like you have to get the trust with your client like I'm your friend. I'm not hurting you. Nursing aid thing is really different from caregiver because here you have the reward. Yes, you earned the money but it's not that it's what you have in heart when you ask her (patient) to do something, she will follow because she established the trust that's what I experienced here that's why I'm really happy.

P2: I could say that it's really nice profession...It's not really easy to be a care giver and you will not be efficient or be effective as a caregiver if you will not do it with your heart..I'm really happy for us. As of now there are no complaints.

P5: I've learned how to be patient, listen supportive, as well as professional and responsible to do my duty...But you know, being a caregiver and being a HATC graduate is the best thing that has ever happened to me..I think those who want to study caregiver or nursing assistant, they need to focus and they need to think as like they love this career, not only because they want to have a course or they

want to have a degree. If you really want to become a caregiver or nursing assistant you must love this course by yourself, because if you love this course and you will love your profession, you will do the best for you and for the residents.

P6: I feel excited and motivated since I started working as a caregiver. I enjoy taking care of my elderly clients because it makes me feel like I'm taking care of my grandparents, something I wasn't able to do before.

P7: I always bear in mind that I need to have patience, love, and compassion to be happy in this job. If you do not have the passion for it you will easily give up especially if you are providing care for the elderly.

P10: I love doing it. I love challenges. Without challenges, you cannot test yourself...You will not learn.

The findings agree with the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2018), which states that being a caregiver requires tolerance, empathy, and reliability, in addition to a strong desire to help people. Dependability, adaptability, and passion are traits of high-achieving caregivers. They must possess outstanding communication skills in order to establish a connection with the individuals they care for, help dispel the social isolation and loneliness experienced by many elderly individuals and listen sympathetically to the particular struggles that older people face.

Based on the results of the study, the written and learned curriculum of HATC Caregiver Training Course are highly aligned in terms of developing the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of students because graduates were able to achieve their main goal of changing career path, that is to be efficient caregivers that served as their ticket to migrating to first world countries. Therefore, it is recommended to have a deeper analysis of the factors that affect the implementation of the written and learned curriculum to have a comprehensive understanding of the alignment between the written and learned curriculum.

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